

Relative Efficacies of Cationic and Anionic Surfactants and Their Mixtures in the Suppression of Polarographic Negative Maximum of Ni(II)

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Manuscript received 19 April 1979, accepted 27 May 1980

The suppression of polarographic negative maximum of Ni(II) has been attempted by various cationic and anionic surfactants viz., Lauryl pyridinium chloride (LPC), Cetyl pyridinium chloride (CPC), Cetyl pyridinium bromide (CPB), Cetyl trimethylammonium bromide (CTAB), Cetyl dimethyl benzyl ammonium chloride (CDBAC), Sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS), Dodecyl benzene sulphonate (DBS), Dioctyl sodium sulpho-succinate (DSSS), Dibutyl sodium sulpho-succinate (DBSS) and Tergitol-7. The relative efficacies of these surfactants and their mixtures have been established on the basis of the value of the kinetic parameter ' αn_a ' calculated by Koutecky's method. A comparison of ' αn_a ' values at the stage where maximum just disappears gives the relative efficacies of cationic and anionic surfactants and also an insight into their additive or antagonistic influence in the mixture.

RAM *et al.*^{1,2} have reported the suppression of polarographic maxima of Ni(II) and Co(II) by various ionic and non-ionic surfactants and have compared their relative efficacies on the basis of characteristic properties viz., maximum suppression point³ (M.S.P.), specific suppression coefficient⁴ (S.S.C.) and critical micelle concentration⁵ (C.M.C.). Dubey *et al.*⁶ have studied the effect of increasing concentrations of some ionic and non-ionic surfactants beyond the concentration just sufficient to eliminate the maxima on the kinetics of the electrode reactions of Ni(II) and Co(II). Recently, Singh and coworkers⁶ have compared the efficacies of some heavy metal cations in the suppression of Ni(II) maximum in terms of kinetic parameter ' αn_a '. However, the efficacies of ionic and non-ionic surfactants in the suppression of Ni(II) maximum have not been investigated quantitatively so far. Moreover, according to Kuta⁷ very interesting results can be obtained if two surfactants of opposite sign are used as suppressors in mixture. Therefore, in the present study an attempt has been made to compare the efficacies of ionic and non-ionic surfactants separately as well as their mixtures.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R., B.D.H. grade and their solutions were prepared in conductivity water. The depolarizer concentration was kept at $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$. NaNO_3 (0.05M) was used as the supporting electrolyte.

A manual polarograph (Toshniwal CL 02) in conjunction with a polyflex galvanometer (Toshniwal PL 50) was used for measuring the potential and

current respectively. Deoxygenation of the solutions was done by passing through the solution a steady stream of purified nitrogen gas. All the measurements were made at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Saturated calomel electrode (S.C.E.) was used as a reference electrode. The d.m.e. had the following characteristics :

$$m = 1.67 \text{ mg/sec, } t = 4.04 \text{ sec, } m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 1.778 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/6}, h_{\text{corr}} = 63.0 \text{ cm.}$$

Results and Discussion

On being suppressed by the requisite amounts of the surfactants, Ni(II) yields, in each case, a well-defined diffusion-controlled wave. On applying various criteria of irreversibility⁸⁻¹¹, it has been ascertained that the electrode reaction of Ni(II) is totally irreversible in the presence of different amounts of cationic and anionic surfactants as well as in their mixtures. The value of the kinetic parameter ' αn_a ' has been calculated by Koutecky's method¹².

From Table I it is evident that ' αn_a ' shows a decrease with increase in the concentration of each surfactant. ' αn_a ' values (and subsequent estimation of ' α ') give a measure of the extent to which kinetics of the electrode reaction is being influenced. An attempt to estimate n_a (the number of electrons involved in the rate determining step) leads to a conclusion that n_a is equal to 2. However, according to Meites¹³ only a single electron can be transferred at a time and a value of n_a exceeding 1 would not necessarily mean that two electrons are actually

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TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF Ni(II) IN THE PRESENCE OF INCREASING CONCENTRATIONS OF CATIONIC AND ANIONIC SURFACTANTS

Surfactants	[Surfactant] M	i_d μA	$\left. \frac{-E_{1/2}}{V} \right $ (S.C.E.)	$D \times 10^6$ cm^2/sec	αn_a
<i>Cationic</i>					
LPC	4.0×10^{-7}	12.09	1.08	5.81	0.64
	1.0×10^{-6}	11.62	1.09	5.33	0.46
CPC	4.0×10^{-7}	11.93	1.08	5.64	0.53
	1.0×10^{-6}	11.62	1.09	5.33	0.46
CPB	5.4×10^{-6}	10.99	1.03	4.79	0.53
	7.0×10^{-6}	10.05	1.04	4.00	0.47
CTAB	8.0×10^{-6}	11.62	1.11	5.33	0.57
	1.0×10^{-5}	8.79	1.17	3.06	0.53
CDBAC	8.0×10^{-6}	11.40	1.07	5.15	0.49
	4.8×10^{-6}	9.88	1.13	3.87	0.47
<i>Anionic</i>					
SLS	2.0×10^{-4}	11.77	1.10	5.49	0.59
	1.0×10^{-3}	10.52	1.14	4.39	0.53
DBS	1.0×10^{-4}	12.87	1.12	6.55	0.49
	1.0×10^{-3}	12.56	1.15	6.25	0.43
Tergitol-7	4.0×10^{-7}	12.54	1.09	6.23	0.64
	1.0×10^{-6}	12.16	1.10	5.85	0.57
DSSS	7.0×10^{-5}	14.23	1.13	8.82	0.46
	1.0×10^{-4}	13.19	1.15	7.62	0.43
DBSS	6.0×10^{-3}	15.38	1.14	8.00	0.61
	1.6×10^{-2}	13.81	1.20	7.56	0.59

* indicates the concentration of surfactant at which the maximum just disappears.

added simultaneously but merely that the successive steps are too nearly simultaneous to be distinguished on the time scale implicit in the polarographic measurement. Since the decrease in αn_a values is indiscrete and at no stage the two consecutive values

vary by a factor of 2, the possibility of decrease in the value of the product αn_a due to the change in n_a is ruled out. Thus it can be safely concluded that it is α which is decreasing¹⁴. α , the transfer coefficient signifies¹⁵ the fraction of the applied voltage which favours the cathodic reaction, $Ni^{2+} + 2e \rightarrow Ni$. A decrease in the value of α thus implies that the transfer of electron/electrons is made increasingly difficult. In other words, the electrode reaction of Ni(II) is rendered increasingly more irreversible. A decrease in i_d and a negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ with an increase in the concentration of both cationic and anionic surfactants lend support to this conclusion.

Relative efficacies of surfactants in terms of αn_a values :

At the stage where maximum of Ni(II) just disappears, the order of αn_a values signifies the extent to which the addition of cationic and anionic surfactants renders the electrode reaction more irreversible from the position in the absence of these surfactants. In other words, a surfactant for which αn_a has got higher value at the point of just suppression will be more effective with minimum influence on the kinetics of the electrode reaction. In the present study the order of αn_a values for different surfactants is as follows :

Cationic : LPC > CPC, CPB > CTAB > CDBAC

Anionic : Tergitol-7 > DBSS, SLS > DBS > DSSS

Thus among the cationic surfactants LPC eliminates

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF Ni(II) IN THE PRESENCE OF MIXTURES OF CATIONIC AND ANIONIC SURFACTANTS

Cationic+Anionic surfactants	[Cationic+Anionic] M	i_d μA	$\frac{-E_{1/2}}{V}$ (S.C.E.)	$D \times 10^6$ cm^2/sec	αn_a
LPC+SLS	$2.0 \times 10^{-7} + 1.0 \times 10^{-4}$	12.25	1.04	5.95	0.81
	$1.0 \times 10^{-6} + 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$	11.62	1.07	5.33	0.74
LPC+DBS	$4.0 \times 10^{-7} + 8.0 \times 10^{-6}$	12.56	1.09	7.10	0.67
	$1.0 \times 10^{-6} + 1.0 \times 10^{-4}$	12.24	1.10	6.72	0.43
CPC+Tergitol-7	$4.0 \times 10^{-6} + 2.0 \times 10^{-7}$	13.34	1.09	7.02	0.64
	$6.0 \times 10^{-9} + 4.0 \times 10^{-7}$	12.56	1.10	6.25	0.49
CPB+DSSS	$4.4 \times 10^{-6} + 6.0 \times 10^{-6}$	12.87	1.12	6.55	0.51
	$7.0 \times 10^{-6} + 1.0 \times 10^{-4}$	12.56	1.21	6.25	0.43
CPC+DSSS	$4.0 \times 10^{-7} + 7.0 \times 10^{-5}$	12.56	1.12	5.95	0.51
	$1.0 \times 10^{-6} + 1.0 \times 10^{-4}$	11.30	1.15	5.06	0.49
CPB+Tergitol-7	$5.0 \times 10^{-7} + 0.5 \times 10^{-7}$	12.56	1.13	6.25	0.55
	$5.0 \times 10^{-6} + 1.5 \times 10^{-6}$	10.83	1.16	6.65	0.47
CTAB+DSSS	$1.0 \times 10^{-7} + 1.0 \times 10^{-4}$	12.56	1.13	6.25	0.67
	$6.0 \times 10^{-7} + 6.0 \times 10^{-4}$	11.30	1.15	5.06	0.57
CTAB+Tergitol-7	$0.5 \times 10^{-7} + 0.5 \times 10^{-7}$	12.54	1.10	6.23	0.64
	$1.0 \times 10^{-6} + 1.0 \times 10^{-6}$	11.40	1.13	5.15	0.57
CDBAC+DSSS	$3.0 \times 10^{-6} + 6.0 \times 10^{-6}$	13.50	1.14	7.23	0.55
	$1.3 \times 10^{-6} + 2.0 \times 10^{-4}$	7.69	1.21	2.34	0.46
CDBAC+Tergitol-7	$1.5 \times 10^{-6} + 1.5 \times 10^{-7}$	15.70	1.06	9.73	0.61
	$2.5 \times 10^{-6} + 2.5 \times 10^{-6}$	14.76	1.07	8.64	0.47
CDBAC+DBSS	$1.5 \times 10^{-6} + 3.0 \times 10^{-3}$	14.76	1.09	8.64	0.64
	$1.2 \times 10^{-6} + 2.3 \times 10^{-2}$	13.66	1.18	7.39	0.61

* indicates the concentration of surfactant at which the maximum just disappears.

the maximum of Ni(II) with minimum influence on the kinetics of the electron transfer followed by CPC, CPB, CTAB and CDBAC. On the other hand, among the anionic surfactants DBSS eliminates the maximum with minimum influence of the kinetics of the electron transfer followed by Tergitol-7, SLS, DBS and DSSS.

A comparison of αn_a values at the point of just suppression in respect of the mixtures of cationic and anionic surfactants shows that their effect is additive in suppressing the maximum except for the mixture of CPB and DSSS where the effect has been found to be antagonistic.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Dr. S. N. Srivastava, Principal, Agra College, Agra for facilities.

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